

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1950	Ana Cano	1971	1975	2016	w	Spanish philologist	
1950	Carol J. Greenhouse	1971	1976	2018	w	American anthropologist (Anthropology, Legal Anthropology)	
1950	Michael Patrick O'Connor	1972	1978	2007		American scholar of the Ancient Near East and a poet	
1950	James P. Leary	1973	1977			American folklorist and scholar of Scandinavian studies	
1950	Gregory R. Guy	1973	1981			American-Canadian linguist (sociolinguistics, historical linguistics, phonetics and phonology)	
1950	Robert A. Brightman	1973	1983	2016		American anthropologist and the Greenberg Professor of Native American Studies	
1950	Gary Macy	1973	1983	2017		American Professor of Religious Studies	
1950	Ruth Wodak	1974	1974	2011	w	Austrian linguist	
1950	Giuliano Pisani	1974	1974			Italian writer, classical philologist, scholar of ancient Greek and Latin literature, and art historian	
1950	John M. Lipski	1974	1974	2017		American linguist (Spanish and Portuguese dialectology and language variation)	
1950	Barry Bogin	1974	1977			American physical anthropologist trained at Temple University who researches physical growth in Guatemalan Maya children, and is a theorist upon the evolutionary origins of human childhood	
1950	Vernon L. Scarborough	1974	1980			American academic anthropologist and archaeologist, known for his research and publications on settlement, land use and water management practices of archaic and Pre-industrial society	
1950	Steven M. Lev Cohen	1974	1974	2018		American-Israeli Jewish sociologist and professor of social policy	
1950	J. Lachlan Mackenzie	1975	1977	2015		British linguist	
1950	JR Martin	1975	1978			Canadian Professor of Linguistics	
1950	Michael Tomasello	1975	1980			American psychologist as linguist	
1950	S.N. Sridhar	1975	1980			Indian Professor of Linguistics and India Studies	
1950	Paul van Geert	1975	1975	2015		Dutch linguist, professor of developmental psychology	

1950	Eve Kosofsky Sedgwick	1975	1975	2009	w	American academic scholar in the fields of gender studies, queer theory (queer studies), and critical theory
1950	Andrew Milner	1976	1977	2013		British-Australian cultural theorist and literary critic (Professor Emeritus of English and Comparative Literature)
1950	Anissava Miltenova	1976	1983		w	Bulgarian Professor of Medieval Studies Institute for Literature
1950	Frances Spalding	1976	1977	2016		British art historian and writer
1950	Miklós Kontra	1976	1987	2015		Hungarian linguist
1950	Riris K. Toha Sarumpaet	1976	1983		w	Indonesian Professor of Literature
1950	Gerald Gazdar	1976	1976	2002		British linguist and computer scientist
1950	Maria Teschler-Nicola	1976	1976	2015	w	Austrian human biologist, anthropologist and ethnologist
1950	Caroline Brettell	1976		2017	w	Canadian cultural anthropologist known for her scholarship on migration and gender
1950	Alessandro Duranti	1977	1981	2016		Italian the Distinguished Professor of Anthropology
1950	Diana Brydon	1977	1977	2012	w	Canadian literary scholar (postcolonial literary and cultural studies, effects of globalization)
1950	Michael Lambek	1977	1978			Canadian anthropologist (religion)
1950	Bonnie Nardi	1977	1977	2018	w	American digital anthropologist (activity theory, interaction design, games, social media, and society and technology)
1950	J. Stephen Lansing	1977	1977	2019		American anthropologist and complexity scientist
1950	Alan R. Rogers	1977	1982			American Professor in the Department of Anthropology and Adjunct Professor in the Department of Biology at the University of Utah
1950	Meaghan Morris	1978	1978	2018	w	Australian scholar of cultural studies (Professor of Gender and Cultural Studies)
1950	Helle Metslang	1978	1978		w	Estonian linguist
1950	Michael S. Rochemont	1978	1978	2018		Canadian linguist (Syntax, Prosody, Pragmatics, Information structure)
1950	Terrence Deacon	1978	1984			American Neuroanthropologist
1950	Mark Baltin	1978	1978			American linguist

1950	Guy Hubert Bailey	1978		2013	American sociolinguist and the 1st president of the University of Texas–Rio Grande Valley
1950	Bencie Woll	1978	1992	2018	w American–British linguist and scholar of sign language
1950	Liza Dalby	1978	1978		w American anthropologist and novelist specializing in Japanese culture
1950	Luisa Maffi	1978	1994		w Italian co-founder and Director of Terralingua, an international NGO devoted to sustaining the biocultural diversity of life - the world's biological, cultural, and linguistic diversity - through research, education, policy-relevant work, and on-the-ground action
1950	Manfred Kremser	1978	1978	2013	Austrian ethnologist and researcher of the human consciousness
1950	Robert Elsie	1978	1978	2014	Canadian-German scholar who specialized in Albanian literature and folklore
1950	Linda Connor	1978	1982	2019	w Australian anthropologist
1950	Richard L. Burger	1978	1978	2020	American archaeologist and anthropologist
1950	Claudine Dauphin	1978		2011	w French archaeologist specialising in the Byzantine period
1950	Patricia Shehan Campbell	1979	1981	2019	American Professor of Music (World Music Pedagogy, Children's Musical Cultures)
1950	Theo D'haen	1979	1981	2015	Belgian Full professor of English and Comparative Literature
1950	Шамина Вера Борисовна	1979	1979		w Russian Professor of Department of Foreign Literature (филология, театроведение)
1950	Wolfram Euler	1979	1979		German historical linguist and Indo-Europeanist
1950	Norbert Hornstein	1979	1979		American linguist
1950	Andrew Rippin	1979	1998	2016	Canadian scholar of Islam
1950	James Geiss	1979	1979	2000	American scholar (Chinese history, specifically on the Ming dynasty (1368-1644 CE))
1950	Ellen Dissanayake	1979	No		w American author and scholar focusing on "the anthropological exploration of art and culture"
1950	Stephen O. Murray	1979	1979	2019	American sociologist, anthropologist, and independent scholar
1950	David Kowal	1980	1980	2012	American Professor of art history

1950 Allan Luke	1980	1985	2015	Canadian-Australian educator, researcher, and theorist studying literacy, multiliteracies, applied linguistics, and educational sociology and policy	
1950 Jing Wang	1980	1985	2005 w	Chinese Professor of of Chinese media and Cultural Studies and S.C. Fang Professor of Chinese Language & Culture	
1950 Merle Collins	1980	1990	2013 w	Grenadian distinguished Grenadian poet and short story writer	
1950 Leona Toker	1980	1980	2012 w	Israeli Professor Emerita of English Literature	
1950 Julie Tetel Andresen	1980	1980	w	American linguistic historiographer and romance novelist	
1950 Barbara Rylko-Bauer	1980	1985	w	American medical anthropologist and author	
1950 Odd Are Berkaak	1980	1980		Norwegian social anthropologist	
1950 Elizabeth Anne McCauley	1980	1980	2018 w	American the David Hunter McAlpin Professor of the History of Photography and Modern Art at Princeton University	
1950 Patri J. Pugliese	1980	1982	2007	American historian of science, dance, and fencing, as well as a teacher of historical dance	1950-2007
1950 Hermann Spieckermann	1980	1982	2019	German biblical scholar, historian of ancient Near Eastern religion, and Protestant theologian	
1950 Robyn Carston	1981	1986	2016 w	New Zealand-British linguist and academic(pragmatics, semantics, and the philosophy of language)	
1950 Tullia Magrini	1981	1992	2005 w	Italian anthropologist (Anthropology of Music)	1950-2005
1950 Zakariyau I. Oseni	1981	1984	2015	Nigerian Arabic and Islamic Studies Scholar, an Imam and a poet	
1950 Jozef Kwaterko	1981	1986	2013	Polish literature historian	
1950 Carl Ernst	1981	1981		American Professor of Religious Studies	
1950 Sandra Lynn Morgen	1982	1982	2016 w	American feminist anthropologist	1950-2016
1950 Matoula Scaltsa	1982	1982	2017 w	Greek Professor of Art History and Museology	
1950 Aihwa Ong	1982	1982	2010 w	Malaysian Sociocultural Anthropology	
1950 Patrice Beddor	1982	1982	w	American Professor of Linguistics (phonology and phonetics)	

1950	Zofia Agnieszka Kłakówna	1983	1983	2017 w	Polish philologist, educational theorist, academic, schoolteacher of Polish language, author of school textbooks	
1950	Kathryn Woolard	1983	1984	2019 w	American Professor of Anthropology	
1950	Brackette F. Williams	1983	1983	w	American Afro Justice Advocate, associate professor of cultural anthropology	
1950	S. Peter Cowe	1983	1983		American the Narekatsi Professor of Armenian Studies	
1950	Salwa El-Gharib	1984	1984	2010 w	Egyptian Applied Arts, President of the International Academy for Engineering and Media Science (IAEMS), 2012-2015	
1950	Rose Mary Allen	1984	2007	w	Dutch (Curaçaoan) anthropologist	
1950	Анатолій Нямцу	1985	1985	2018	Ukrainian linguist	1950-2018
1950	Inoslav Bešker	1985	2001		Croatian Professor of philology and journalist	
1950	Abdul Kadir	1985	1985	2014	Ugandian social activist and translator	1950-2014
1950	Donny George Youkhanna	1985	1995	2011	Iraqi-Assyrian archaeologist, anthropologist, author, curator, and scholar	1950-2011
1950	Annaclara Cataldi Palau	1985		2018 w	Italian palaeographer specialising in Greek mediaeval and renaissance palaeography and history of the book	
1950	Estelle Lazer	1985	1985	2018 w	Australian archaeologist and physical anthropologist	
1950	Eric Walter Rothenbuhler	1985	1985	2014	American anthropologist and dean of the School of Communications and a professor at Webster University	
1950	Gloria Goodwin Raheja	1985	1985	2019 w	American anthropologist who specializes in ethnographic history	
1950	Pamela Faber	1986	1986	2017 w	American-Spanish linguist (Computational Linguistics, Translation)	
1950	Malka Muchnik	1986	1992	2012 w	Argentinean Associate Professor, Hebrew and Semitic Languages	
1950	Чернышова Алефтина Юрьевна	1986	1986	w	Russian professor of Russian language and applied linguistics (синтаксис русского языка, культурология)	
1950	Jenny Sharpe	1987	1987	w	American professor of English and Comparative Literature	
1950	Alex Lascarides	1987	1988	2018 w	British Professor of Semantics (Computational Linguistics, semantics, pragmatics)	

1950	Anne Allison	1987	1987	2005 w	American professor of cultural anthropology	
1950	Kathy O'Dell	1988	1992	2014 w	American art historian, theorist, curator, arts advocate, author (the Dean for Arts Partnerships)	
1950	Peeter Torop	1989	1995	2015	Estonian semiotician	
1950	Bruce J. Ellis	1989	1995	2017	American Professor of Psychology and Anthropology	
1950	George Legrady	1990			Canadian born-Hungarian multidisciplinary digital media artist and university professor in photography and computational media arts	
1950	Cleo Odzer	1990	1990	2001 w	American writer and culture anthropologist	1950-2001
1950	Tidiane N'Diaye	1990			Franco-Senegalese anthropologist, economist, and writer	
1950	Barbara Bolt	1991	2002	w	Australian Associate Dean of Research, Faculty of Fine Arts and Music	
1950	Sven Tarp	1991	2006		Danish linguist (Lexicography)	
1950	Scott Kiesling	1992	1996		American professor in the Department of Linguistics	
1950	Felicity Jenz	1992	1992	w	German Research Fellow, Cluster of Excellence Religion and Politics	
1950	Lina Choueiri	1994	2001	w	Lebanese linguist	
1950	Terry Rey	1996	1996		French Professor of Religion	
1950	Lameen SOUAG	2002	2010		French Linguist (Berber and Arabic)	
1950	Sebastian Groes	2004	2005		British Senior Lecturer in English Literature	
1951	Галиуллин Камиль Рахимович	1971	1982		Russian philologist (прикладная лингвистика, лингвография, компьютерная лингвистика)	
1951	Dick Hebdige	1973	No	2016	British media theorist and sociologist	
1951	John A. Goldsmith	1973	1976	2017	American computational linguist (Phonology, Generative grammar)	
1951	Vintilă Mihăilescu	1973		2020	Romanian cultural anthropologist	
1951	Janice Boddy	1974	1982	2016 w	Canadian anthropologist	
1951	Michael Kimmel	1974	1981		American sociologist specializing in gender studies	
1951	Brian Joseph	1975	1978	2016	American historical linguistics	
1951	David Nash	1975	1980	2015	Australian linguist	
1951	HE Janse van Vuuren	1975		2016 w	South African Professor of Afrikaans & Dutch Literature	
1951	Pierre Pica	1975	1985		French linguist (National Center for Scientific Research)	

1951	Lars Ole Bonde	1975	2005	2018	Danish Emeritus professor, music therapy
1951	Jeremy Black	1975	1980	2004	British Assyriologist and Sumerologist, founder of the online Electronic Text Corpus of Sumerian Literature
1951	Carla Obermeyer	1975	1988	w	Lebanese medical anthropologist and epidemiologist specializing in the study of fertility and HIV
1951	Douglas W. Owsley	1975	1978		American anthropologist who is the current Head of Physical Anthropology at the Smithsonian's National Museum of Natural History (NMNH)
1951	Stewart M Hoover	1975	1985		American Professor of Media Studies and Religious Studies
1951	Robert Lecker	1976	1980		Canadian scholar, author, and Greenshields Professor of English
1951	Udaya Narayana Singh	1976	1979	2013	Indian major linguist, translator, lexicographer & creative writer
1951	John Goldsmith	1976	1976	2018	American linguist (phonology, computational linguistics)
1951	Vera Zobotkina	1976	1979	w	Russian linguist, philologist, semiotician
1951	Suzanne Romaine	1976	1981	2014 w	American linguist (historical linguistics and sociolinguistics)
1951	Blair A. Rudes	1976	1976	2008	American linguist (Native American languages)
1951	Emmanuel Todd	1976	1976		French historian, anthropologist, demographer, sociologist and political scientist
1951	David Lucking	1977	1977	2015	Italian Professor of English Literature
1951	Edward Chaney	1977	1985	2019	British cultural historian
1951	James Phelan	1977	1977	2018	American literary scholar
1951	Geoffrey Horrocks	1977	1977		British Linguist, classical philologist, Byzantine and neo-Gracist
1951	Ignacio Bosque	1977	1978		Spanish linguist
1951	Laurent Sagart	1977	1977		French researcher in Chinese linguistics and Austronesian languages
1951	Nigel Goring-Morris	1977	1986		British-Israeli archaeologist
1951	Ronny Velásquez	1977			Venezuelan anthropologist, scientific explorer and editor.

1951 Robert A. Rubinstein	1977	1977		American cultural anthropologist whose work bridges the areas of political and medical anthropology, and the history and theory of the discipline
1951 Annie Bélis	1977	1982	w	French archaeologist, philologist, papyrologist and musician
1951 Stuart Charme	1977	1980		American Professor of Religion
1951 Curtis Roads	1978	No	2016	American composer, author and computer programmer
1951 Ellen Douglas-Cowie	1978	1978	2016 w	British linguist (linguistics expert, Ellen's range of topics includes spoken English, phonetics and sociolinguistics)
1951 Marjorie Levinson	1978	1978	2012 w	American the F. L. Huetwell Professor of English
1951 Irving Finkel	1978			British philologist and Assyriologist
1951 William Dressler	1978	1978	2019	American anthropologist known for his concept of cultural consonance and work on cultural models especially in the context of medical anthropology
1951 Daniel L. Everett	1979	1980	2018	American linguist
1951 John Nerbonne	1980		2017	American computational linguist
1951 Kees de Bot	1980	1982	2019	Dutch linguist (bilingualism)
1951 Ceil Lucas	1980	1980	2014	American Linguist
1951 Thomas G. Palaima	1980	1980	2020	American Mycenologist, the Robert M. Armstrong Centennial Professor and the founding director of the University's Program in Aegean Scripts and Prehistory (PASP)
1951 Gay Robins	1980	1981	2018 w	British the Samuel Candler Dobbs Professor of Art History at Emory University
1951 Friederike Hassauer	1980	1980	w	German literary scholar and professor for Romance Philology
1951 Paul L Swanson	1981	1985		American Professor (Studies in Religion and Culture)
1951 Katica Kulavkova	1981	1996	2015 w	North Macedonian writer and academic (theory of literature)
1951 Erika Hoff	1981	1981	w	American developmental psychologist and an expert on language development and bilingualism
1951 Sandra Guardini T. Vasconcelos	1982	1991	2008 w	Brazilian Professor of English and Comparative Literature

1951	Setiawan Sabana	1982	2002		Indonesian professor in Seni Rupa ITB and teaches graphic art		
1951	Einar Thomassen	1982	1982		Norwegian religious studies scholar		
1951	Andries van Aarde	1982	1983	2017	South African honorary professor of theology and a research fellow		
1951	Gina Wisker	1983	1983	2015	w	British Professor of Contemporary Literature and Higher Education	
1951	Peter T. Daniels	1983				American scholar of writing systems (typology)	
1951	Nurit Bird-David	1983	1983		w	Israeli professor of cultural anthropology	
1951	Edit Doron	1983	1983	2013	w	Israeli academic specializing in linguistics	1951-2019
1951	Theodore C. Bestor	1983	1983	2017		American Professor of Anthropology and Japanese Studies	
1951	Andrew Wallace-Hadrill	1983				British ancient historian, classical archaeologist, and academic	
1951	Peter G. Riddell	1984	1990			Canadian Senior Research Fellow of Melbourne School of Theology	
1951	Shoichi Iwasaki	1984	1984	2013		Japanese Professor of UCLA (Center for World Languages)	
1951	Jerome Packard	1984	1984			American linguist (Chinese linguistics and psycholinguistics)	
1951	Rita Segato	1984	1984		w	Argentinean-Brazilian academic, who has been called "one of Latin America's most celebrated feminist anthropologists" and "one of the most lucid feminist thinkers of this era"	
1951	Evelyn Blackwood	1984	1993	2017	w	American anthropologist whose research focuses on gender, sexuality, identity, and kinship	
1951	R. Brian Ferguson	1984	1988			American anthropologist	
1951	John S. Kloppenborg	1984	1984			Canadian professor of religion	
1951	Roman Malek	1984	1984			Polish-German professor and sinologist	1951-2019
1951	Hamid Dabashi	1984	1984			Iranian Professor of Iranian Studies and Comparative Literature	
1951	Timothy Brook	1984	1984			Canadian historian, sinologist, and writer specializing in the study of China (sinology)	
1951	Douglas Kahn	1985	1997	2016		American-Australian Professor of Media and Innovation	
1951	Peter Goin	1986	No			American Writer, photographer, and educator	

1951	Nedžad Leko	1986	1986		Bosnian linguist		
1951	Thomas A. Abercrombie	1986	1986	2019	American associate professor of anthropology	1951-2019	
1951	Robbie Davis-Floyd	1986	1986	w	American cultural, medical, and reproductive anthropologist, researcher, author, and international speaker primarily known for her research on childbirth, midwifery, and obstetrics		
1951	Wendy Orent	1986	1986	2012	w	American anthropologist and author with special interest in pandemics	
1951	Patricia O'Connell Killen	1986			w	American Professor of Religious Studies	
1951	Clayton Valli	1987	1993	2003		American prominent deaf linguist and American Sign Language (ASL) poet	1951-2003
1951	Paul Apodaca	1987	1999			American Native associate professor of Anthropology and American Studies	
1951	Christoph Auffarth	1987	1987			German religious scholar and theologian	
1951	Vera Turković	1988	1992	w		Croatian associate professor at the Academy of Fine Arts (sociology of culture, sociology of art and aesthetics)	
1951	Tom Eide	1988	1989			Norwegian Professor of leadership, ethics and literature	
1951	Ron Highfield	1988	1988			American Professor of Religion	
1951	Larry Nesper	1989	1994			American Professor of Anthropology and American Indian Studies	
1951	Ken Hyland	1990	1995			British-New Zealand linguist	
1951	Teresa Colomer	1990	1993	w		Spanish Doctorate in Educational Sciences (children's literature, Didactic reading of literature)	
1951	Edwin Gentzler	1990	1990	2017		American Professor Emeritus of Comparative Literature	
1951	Appel Włodzimierz	1991				Polish Professor of Classical Philology	
1951	Marcia Pally	1995	1995	w		American professor at the New York University Steinhardt School of Culture, Education, and Human Development	
1952	Irma McClaurin	1971	1993	2016	w	American poet, anthropologist, academic, and leadership consultant	
1952	Ulrich Seelbach	1972	1984	2016		German Professor for German Literature and Linguistics	

1952	José María Sánchez Carrión	1972	1987		Spanish linguist (Basque language, sociolinguistics, historical linguistics)
1952	Robert Van Valin Jr	1972	1977		American linguist and the principal researcher (syntax, semantics, cognitive linguistics)
1952	Glenn W. Most	1972	1980		American classicist and comparatist
1952	Ruth Scodel	1972	1978	2019	w American Classics scholar, and the D.R. Shackleton-Bailey Collegiate Professor of Greek and Latin
1952	Mihhail Lotman	1973	2000	2015	Estonian literature researcher and politician
1952	Ana María Groot	1974	2008		w Colombian historian, archaeologist, anthropologist and associate professor at the Department of Anthropology
1952	Jef Verschueren	1975	1980	2017	Belgian linguist
1952	Luc Steels	1975			Belgian scientist and artist, and Director of the Artificial Intelligence Laboratory
1952	Mary Miller	1975	1981		w American art historian and academician specializing in Mesoamerica and the Maya
1952	Levon Chookaszian	1975	1982		Armenian art historian and the UNESCO Chair of Armenian Art History (UNESCO CAAH)
1952	Luigi Rizzi	1976	1982		Italian linguist
1952	Patricia Keating	1976	1980	2019	w American linguist and noted phonetician
1952	Edgar Radtke	1976	1976	2017	Italian scholar in philology, linguistics and literary criticism Philology of Italian literature
1952	Elizabeth Cowper	1976	1976	2014	w Canadian linguist
1952	Anna Tsing	1976	1984	2018	w American anthropologist
1952	Carlo Severi	1976	1976		Italian anthropologist who is Professor at the Ecole des Hautes Etudes en Sciences Sociales (EHESS)
1952	Jim McGuigan	1977	1985	2017	British Professor of Cultural Analysis, Social Sciences
1952	Susan Makov	1977	No	2015	w American Professor Emeritus of Visual Arts (photographer, printmaker, and painter)
1952	Virginia R. Domínguez	1977	1979		w American political and legal anthropologist
1952	Colin Mercer	1977		2013	w Australian Professor of Cultural Policy and Director, Cultural Policy and Planning Research Unit
1952	Sharon Welch	1977			American Professor of Religion and Society Meadville Lombard Theological School
1952	Mislav Ježić	1977	1983		Croatian Professor of Indology, Philosophy and Religious Studies

1952	Trinidad Barrera	1978	1978	w	Spanish Professor of Literature
1952	Earl Jeffrey Richards	1978	1978	2019	American comparative literature educator (Professor of Romance Literatures)
1952	John W Du Bois	1978	1981		American professor of linguistics
1952	Lyn Frazier	1978	1978	w	American experimental linguist (psycholinguistic research of adult sentence comprehension)
1952	Lawrence Solan	1978	1978		American the Don Forchelli Professor of Law and Director of the Center for the Study of Law, Language and Cognition
1952	Ellen Gruenbaum	1978	1982	2019 w	American the Goldwin Smith Professor of Anthropology and Director of the Institute for European Studies at Cornell University
1952	Philip Russell Hardie	1978		2014	British specialist in Latin literature at the University of Cambridge
1952	Samuel Pfeifer	1978			Swiss Professor für Religion und Psychotherapie
1952	Margit Warburg	1978	1979	w	Danish sociologist of religion
1952	Hagit Borer	1979	1981	2017 w	Israeli-American professor of linguistics
1952	Robert N. McCauley	1979	1979		American professor of philosophy, psychology, religion, and anthropology, pioneer in the cognitive science of religion
1952	William F. Hanks	1979	1983		American linguist and anthropologist
1952	Faye Ginsburg	1979	1986	w	American anthropologist who has devoted her life to the exploration of different cultures and individuals' styles of life
1952	Andre Gingrich	1979	1979	2017	Austrian ethnologist and anthropologist
1952	John Pultz	1980	1993		American art historian, curator, and critic (history of photo)
1952	Saralyn Reece Hardy	1980	No	w	American Director, Spencer Museum of Art
1952	Thomas Swiss	1980	1983	2015	American poet and writer (former Professor of Culture and Teaching)
1952	Catherine Lutz	1980	1980	w	American Professor of Anthropology and International Studies
1952	Barbara Johnstone	1980	1980	2018 w	American professor of rhetoric and linguistics
1952	Ziba Mir-Hosseini	1980	1980	2012 w	Iranian legal anthropologist, specialising in Islamic law, gender and development

1952	Alan H. Goodman	1980			American biological anthropologist	
1952	Clark Spencer Larsen	1980	1980		American biological anthropologist, author, and educator	
1952	Attash Durrani	1980	1991	2018	Pakistani linguist, researcher, critic and author, educationist and gemologist	1952-2018
1952	Irven Resnick	1980			American Professor of Philosophy and Religion	
1952	John Tooby	1981	1989	2013	American anthropologist (founder of the field of Evolutionary Psychology)	
1952	Douglas Biber	1981	1984		American Regents' Professor Applied Linguistics	
1952	Talbot Taylor	1981	1982		British Professor of English and Linguistics	
1952	Бондар Олександр Іванович	1981		2013	Ukrainian linguist	1952-2013
1952	Rex E. Wallace	1981	1984	2018	American linguist and classical scholar (Etruscan language, languages of ancient Italy, epigraphy, historical linguistics)	
1952	Bart Moore-Gilbert	1981		2015	Tanzanian-British academic, orientalist and political campaigner, most widely known for his work in the field of postcolonial literary studies and theory	1952-2015
1952	Alain Bertho	1981	1994		French anthropologist (urban anthropology, political anthropology, anthropology of globalization and alter-globalization)	
1952	Arturo Escobar	1981	1987		Colombian-American anthropologist and the Kenan Distinguished Professor of Anthropology	
1952	Richard Guy Condon	1981	1981	1995	American Anthropologist	1952-1995
1952	Ritchie Robertson	1981	1981		British the Taylor Professor of the German Language and Literature	
1952	Christa Agnes Tuczay	1981	1981	w	Austrian University professor in Medieval German Language and Literature at the Institute of German Studies	
1952	Birgit Anette Olsen	1981	1999	w	Danish linguist, professor at the University of Copenhagen and leader of the Roots of Europe research center	
1952	Anne Cranny-Francis	1982	1984	2018 w	Australian Professor of Cultural Studies	
1952	Daniel Chandler	1982	1993	2019	British visual semiotician (study of sign process (semiosis))	

1952	Mohamad Hatta Azad Khan	1982	1994		Malaysian Film director, Rector of the National Academy of Cultural and Heritage Arts	
1952	Ofelia Zepeda	1982	1984	w	American (Indianish) Head of American Indian Studies (Tohono O'odham poet and intellectual)	
1952	Dr Chiramel Paul Jose	1982	1991	2017	Indian Professor of English Literature	
1952	Александр Евгеньевич АНИКИН	1982	1984		Russian literature critic, specialist in the field of etymology of Russian vocabulary, contacts of the Russian language and languages of Siberia	
1952	Stamos Metzidakis	1982	1982	2019	American Professor Emeritus of French and Comparative Literature	
1952	Sameer Al Eisa	1982	1982		Egyptian researcher of Department of English Language and Literature	
1952	Scott Atran	1982	1984	2017	American-French cultural anthropologist	
1952	Ann Taves	1982	1983	2017 w	American Professor of Religious Studies	
1952	Lila Abu-Lughod	1983	1984	w	Palestinian-American anthropologist (historical, social, and ideological contexts)	
1952	Eric Vatikiotis-Bateson	1983	1987	2017	Canadian linguist (Communicative expression in language and music)	1952-2017
1952	Yousef Bader	1983	1984		Jordanian Full Professor of English Linguistics	
1952	Helen Spencer-Oatey	1983	1992	w	British Professor of Applied Linguistics (psycholinguistics)	
1952	Heinz Giegerich	1983	1983	2019	British-German linguist	
1952	Edward L. Shaughnessy	1983	1983		American Sinologist, scholar, and educator	
1952	Katya Gibel Mevorach	1983	1991	2019 w	American Professor of Anthropology and American Studies	
1952	Susan Hood	1984	2004	2017 w	Australian Applied Linguistics and TESOL	
1952	Helga Schröder	1984	2004	w	German Senior Lecturer at the Department of Linguistics and Languages, Literacy consultant	
1952	Eric Pennington	1984	1987		Mexican Associate Professor of Latin American and Latino/a Studies, and Spanish Literature	
1952	Rolf Inge Godøy	1984			Norwegian musicologist	
1952	Denys Zacharopoulos	1984			Greek-French art historian and theorist	
1952	Stephen Emmel	1984	1993		American Coptologist and musician	
1952	Stephen F. Jones	1984	1984		American Chair of Russian and Eurasian Studies	
1952	Michael Bonner	1984	1987	2019	American Jewish scholar of Islamic studies	1952-2019

1952	Malan Marnersdóttir	1985		w	Faroese academic, feminist and non-fiction writer		
1952	Hallgerður Gísladóttir	1985	1991	2007	w	Icelandic ethnologist (Icelandic food traditions and gastronomy, and Icelandic man-made caves) and poet	1952-2007
1952	Ira Jacknis	1985	1989			American anthropologist who studies Native American art of the Northwest Coast	
1952	Sherry Farrell Racette	1985	2004		w	Canadian Métis feminist scholar, author, and artist	
1952	Mark R. Woodward	1985	1985			American academic and author of Islam in Java	
1952	Michael A. Messner	1985	1985			American Professor of Sociology and Gender Studies	
1952	L. Oladipo Salami	1986	1987			Nigerian Professor of Language and Linguistics	
1952	Radojka Vukčević	1986	1986	2017	w	Serbian professor of american literature	
1952	Mahendra Kumar Mishra	1987	1987			Indian Folklorist and National Consultant on Multilingual Education (Indigenous studies, multilingual education, indian folklore, oral epics)	
1952	Jasna Jeličić Radonić	1990				Croatian Professor of Ancient Art	
1952	Petr Kylvoušek	1992	1994			Czech Professor of French and French Canadian Literature	
1952	George E. Lewis	1993	2017			American composer, electronic performer, installation artist, trombone player, and scholar (musicology)	
1952	Halyna Lozko	1994	1996		w	Ukrainian ethnologist, theologian and neopagan leader	
1952	Dorothee Beermann	1997	1997		w	Norwegian computational linguist	
1952	Joseph Tonda	2000	2005			Congolese-Gabonese scholar in Congolese and Gabonese culture, society, and politics, and is currently professor of sociology	
1953	Robert Stockman	1974	1990			American scholar specializing in Bahá'í studies who has been called "the foremost historian of the Bahá'í Faith in America."	
1953	Johan van der Auwera	1975	1980	2018		Belgian emeritus professor of General and English Linguistics	
1953	Judy Kegl	1975	1985	2015	w	American linguist (Nicaraguan sign language)	
1953	Nunzio La Fauci	1975	1975			Italian linguist	
1953	Сергей А Старостин	1975	1979	2005		Russian historical linguist and philologist, reconstructor of hypothetical proto-languages	
1953	Anna Szabolcsi	1976	1987		w	Hungarian linguist (semantics, syntax, and the syntax-semantics interface)	
1953	Jean-Jacques Hublin	1976	1978	2019		French Paleoanthropologist	

1953	Alison Galloway	1976	1988	2018	w	American forensic anthropologist
1953	Josep Palomero	1976	2016			Spanish Valencian linguist and vice-president of the Valencian Language Academy
1953	Cary Mazer	1977	1980	2018	w	American associate professor of theatre arts and English
1953	Nick C. Ellis	1977	1978			British (Welsh) psycholinguist
1953	Paitoon M. Chaiyanara	1977	1992			Malaysian Associate Professor in the Department of Malay Language and Culture
1953	Staf Hellemans	1977	1990	2019		Belgian Professor in the Sociology of Religion
1953	Joseph Elie Aoun	1978	1981			Lebanese theoretical syntactician (logical form and wh-movement)
1953	Charles L. Briggs	1978	1981			American anthropologist, Chair of the Ethnic Studies Department at University of California
1953	Peri J. Bearman	1978			w	American academic scholar of Islamic law
1953	Cliff Goddard	1979	1986	2018		Australian linguist
1953	Hubert Haider	1979	1984	2018		Austrian linguist (Syntax, Psycholinguistics, Computational linguistics, Neurolinguistics)
1953	Martin Everaer	1979	1979			Dutch professor Linguistics (Lexicon and Syntax)
1953	Peter Beilharz	1979	1984	2018		Australian sociologist (Professor of Culture and Society)
1953	John McCarthy	1979	1979			American linguist (phonology, morphology, optimality theory)
1953	Chris Hann	1979	1979			British Welsh social anthropologist who has done field research in socialist and post-socialist Eastern Europe (especially in Hungary and Poland) and the Turkic-speaking world
1953	Robert K. Ritner	1979	1987			American Egyptologist
1953	Jon Haarberg	1980	1985			Norwegian professor of general literature
1953	Laurel Brinton	1980	1981	2015	w	American-Canadian linguist
1953	Kinga Fabó	1980	No		w	Hungarian poet, linguist and essayist
1953	Leonard Lewisohn	1980		2018		American author, translator and lecturer in the area of Islamic studies and a specialist in Persian language and Sufi literature
1953	Stephen Halliwell	1980	1980			British classicist and academic

1953-2018

1953 Robin Gerster	1981	1985		Australian author and academic (Professor at the School of Languages, Literatures, Cultures and Linguistics)	
1953 Fröhlich Gerhard	1981	1981		Austrian cultural theorist and science researcher	
1953 Donna B. Gerdts	1981	1981	2016 w	American professor of linguistics and associate director of the First Nations Languages Program	
1953 Paul Mattei	1981			French Latinist, professor of Latin language and literature	
1953 Francine Saillant	1981	1987	w	Canadian anthropologist and intellectual	
1953 Kris L. Hardin	1981	1987	2012 w	American anthropologist and writer, Fellow of the Royal Geographical Society, and an associate professor of anthropology	1953-2012
1953 Pauline Turner Strong	1981	1992	w	American anthropologist specializing in literary, historical, ethnographic, media, and popular representations of Native Americans	
1953 Leo Chavez	1981	1982		American anthropologist, author, and professor, best known for his work in international migration, particularly among Latin American immigrants	
1953 Gregory Cochran	1981	1981	2015	American physicist and anthropologist and author who argues that cultural innovation resulted in new and constantly shifting selection pressures for genetic change, thereby accelerating human evolution and divergence between human races	
1953 James R. Russell	1981	1982	2016	American scholar and professor in Ancient Near Eastern, Iranian and Armenian Studies	
1953 Gudrun Krämer	1981	1981	2019 w	German scholar of Islamic history and co-editor of the third edition of the Encyclopaedia of Islam	
1953 Birgit Anette Olsen	1981	1999	w	Danish linguist, professor at the University of Copenhagen	
1953 Mary E Beckman	1982	1984	2018 w	American Professor of Linguistics	
1953 Regenia Gagnier	1982	1991	w	British Professor of English Language and Literature	
1953 Pertti Anttonen	1982	1993		Finnish folklorist	
1953 Gennaro Chierchia	1982	1984		Italian linguist	
1953 Mahasen Abu-Mansour	1982	1987	2013	Saudi Arabian linguistics educator	

1953	Михайлин Ігор Леонідович	1982	1982	2017	Ukrainian journalist, literary critic	1953-2017
1953	Kim Hill	1982	1983	2010	American Professor of Anthropology School of Human Evolution and Social Change (human evolutionary ecology)	
1953	Susan Hunston	1982	1989	w	British linguist	
1953	Darrell Hamamoto	1982	1987	2018	American orientalist and writer	
1953	Stephen Sewell	1983	2017		Australian playwright and screenwriter	
1953	Luba Freedman	1983	1992	w	Israeli-Russian Professor of Art History, educator	
1953	Anna Dąbrowska	1983	1984	w	Polish philologist (glottodidactics and modern Polish language)	
1953	Ocke-Schwen Bohn	1983	1983		Swedish linguist	
1953	Thomas Højrup	1983			Danish ethnologist	
1953	Georg Wöhrle	1983	1983	2018	German philologist and medical historian	
1953	Craig Broyles	1983			Canadian Professor of Religious Studies	
1953	Daniel Cozort	1983	1986		American Professor of Comparative Religion	
1953	Don Paul Fowler	1983		1999	British English classicist	1953-1999
1953	Brian Nolan	1984	1984	2019	Irish former Head of Department of Informatics and Creative Digital Media	
1953	Juan Mauricio Renold	1984		2019	Argentinian social anthropologist	
1953	Hartmut Wickert	1985	No	2019	German theater director, professor, and director of the performing arts and film department at the Zurich University of the Arts	
1953	Reuven Snir	1985	1987		Israeli Jewish academic, Professor of Arabic language and Arabic literature	
1953	Brigitte Mral	1985	1986	w	German professor of rhetoric	
1953	Carmen Guarini	1985		w	Argentinean anthropologist, teacher, film director, and film producer specializing in anthropological documentary films	
1953	Sonia Elizabeth Guillén	1985	1992	w	Peruvian forensic anthropologist	
1953	Douglas Oakman	1985	1986		American Professor of Religion	
1953	Constantine Mwikamba	1985	1985		Kenyan Lecturer of Philosophy and Religious Studies	
1953	John Kelsay	1985	1985		American Research Professor and Richard L. Rubenstein Professor of Religion	
1953	Caroline Féry	1986	1989	w	German Senior professor of Linguistics (Phonology)	

1953 Luule Epner	1987	1987	w	Estonian theater scholar and literary scholar	
1953 Joga Singh	1987	1993	2018	Indian Professor of Linguistics	
1953 Susan Manning	1987	1987	2013 w	British Scottish academic specialising in Scottish studies and English literature	1953-2013
1953 András Rényi	1988	1994		Hungarian Professor of Art History	
1953 William J. Dominik	1988	1989	2015	American-Australian scholar of Classical Studies	
1953 Dominique de Courcelles	1988	1988	w	French historian of ideas	
1953 Feride Guven	1988	No	w	Turkish Instructor of Department of Modern Languages	
1953 Hillary Rodrigues	1988	1994		Canadian Professor of Religious Studies	
1953 Hella Olbertz	1989		w	Dutch linguist	
1953 James Quesada	1989	1994		Nicaraguan American Anthropologist	
1953 Nancy L. Wicker	1989	1990	w	American professor of art history	
1953 Danie Goosen	1989	1989		South African Professor of Religious Studies	
1953 Linda L. Barnes	1990	1995	w	American medical anthropologist, religion scholar, historian	
1953 Brian Stanley	1990	1992		British historian (history of Christian missions and world Christianity)	
1953 Julijana Vučo	1991	1997	w	Serbian Professor of Italian and Educational Linguistics, translator	
1953 William Melaney	1992	1993		American Professor of English and Comparative Literature	
1953 Victor Olaru	1992	1998		Romanian Professor of English and American Literature (English literature, American literature, Literary Translation)	
1953 Dorin Ștefănescu	1994	2003		Romanian literary essayist and critic	
1953 Lisa Rofel	1994		2018 w	American anthropologist, specialising in feminist anthropology and gender studies	
1953 Andrew Spicer	1997	1998		American Professor of Organisational Behaviour (organisational culture, employee identity, the creation of new organizational forms, space and architecture plays at work and leadership)	
1953 Savka Blagojevic	1997	2001	w	Serbian Professor of English language	
1953 Odey Veronica Ebi	2013		w	Nigerian Senior Lecturer of Modern Languages and Translation Studies	

1954	Volker Sommer	1973	1985	2019	German anthropologist and Professor of Evolutionary Anthropology
1954	Bruce Wayne Hawkins	1975	1984		American linguist
1954	Simon J. Bronner	1976	1981	2009	American folklorist, ethnologist, historian, sociologist, educator
1954	Jean-François Chevrier	1976			French art historian, art critic and exhibition curator
1954	Vivien Anne Law	1977	1979	2002	w British linguist and academic (grammar)
1954	Serban Nichifor	1977	1994		Romanian composer, cellist and music educator
1954	Ali S. Asani	1977	1984		Kenyan Professor of Indo-Muslim Religion and Cultures and the Director of Prince Alwaleed bin Talal Islamic Studies Program at Harvard University
1954	Gail Stavitsky	1978	1990	2015	w American Chief Curator at the Montclair Art Museum
1954	Tim Stowell	1978	1981		Canadian linguist (nature of syntactic structure and its relation to semantic interpretation)
1954	Larry Polansky	1978			American composer, guitarist, mandolinist, and a professor
1954	Irene Heim	1978	1982	2004	w American linguist and noted specialist in semantics
1954	Dorinne K. Kondo	1978	1982		w American Professor of Anthropology and American Studies
1954	Scott Cane	1978	1984		Australian archaeologist and anthropologist
1954	Valerie Hoffman	1978	1986		w American professor who specializes in Islamic thought and practice
1954	Janet B. Pierrehumbert	1979	1980		w New Zealand Professor of Language Modelling (Phonology, Phonetics, Cognitive Science)
1954	Linda Kay Watts	1979	1992	2016	w American anthropologist (Cultural and Linguistic Anthropology)
1954	Sheila Embleton	1979	1981		w Canadian-British linguist
1954	Steven Pinker	1979	1979		Canadian-American cognitive psychologist, linguist, and popular science author
1954	Lisbeth Haas	1979	1986		w American historian and anthropologist
1954	Gary A. Olson	1980	1980		American scholar of rhetoric and culture
1954	Pamela Davidson	1980	1984		w British Professor of Russian Literature at the School of Slavonic and East European Studies
1954	Edgar Schneider	1980	1981		Austrian-German linguist
1954	Péter Siptár	1980	1982		Hungarian linguist

1954 Michael Brody	1980	1982	2010	Hungarian linguist
1954 Rochelle Lieber	1980	1980	w	American linguist
1954 Kevin Tuite	1980	1988		Irish-Canadian full Professor of Anthropology (Caucasian languages, Georgian language)
1954 Ien Ang	1980	1980	2012 w	Indonesian Professor of Cultural Studies
1954 Vincent Gillespie	1980			British the J. R. R. Tolkien Professor of English Literature and Language
1954 Françoise Pommaret	1980	1984	w	French ethno-historian and Tibetologist
1954 Lissant Bolton	1980	1994	w	Australian anthropologist and the Keeper of the Department of Africa, Oceania and the Americas at the British Museum
1954 Guillermo Algaze	1980	1986		Cuban-American anthropologist
1954 Rudolf Simek	1980	1980		Austrian Germanist and philologist
1954 Christopher Chapple	1980	1980		American Indologist and scholar of the renouncing religions of India, namely yoga, Jainism and Buddhism
1954 Mehmed Aksamija	1981	1981		Bosnian pedagogue, historian, art theorist and master photographer, founder and regular member of the Bosnian Academy of Sciences and Arts (BANU)
1954 David Huron	1981	1989		Canadian Arts and Humanities Distinguished Professor
1954 Heinrich Pfandl	1981			Austrian Professor of Slavic philology (Russian language, Slovenian language, Language contact, History of Slavic languages, Phraseology)
1954 Jurij Fikfak	1981	1999		Slovenian ethnologist (Ethnology, cultural anthropology, Folklore, qualitative research, history of science)
1954 David Odden	1981	1981		American linguist
1954 Michael Bünker	1981	1981		Austrian theologian
1954 Peter Lampe	1981	1989		German Protestant theologian and Professor of New Testament Studies
1954 Ruby Blondell	1981	1984	w	American Professor of Classics, Adjunct Professor of Gender, Women, & Sexuality Studies
1954 Christopher Alan Waterman	1982	1986	2015	American anthropologist and musician (music and culture in Africa and the Americas)

1954	Evelyn O'Callaghan	1982		w	Jamaican academic (professor of West Indian literatur)	
1954	Alicja Sakaguchi	1982	1982	w	Polish linguist (interlinguistics, Esperanto)	
1954	Mary Dalrymple	1982	1990	w	British linguist (linguistics and computational linguistics and centers mainly on grammar development, syntax, semantics and the syntax-semantics interface)	
1954	Odd Einar Haugen	1982	1982		Norwegian professor of Old Norse Philology	
1954	Jan Inge Sørnbø	1982	1982		Norwegian philologist, author and poet	
1954	Greg Myers	1982	1982	2017	American linguist	
1954	Alison Wylie	1982	1982	2017 w	Canadian researcher in philosophy of science, research ethics, and feminism in the social sciences, particularly archaeology and anthropology	
1954	Inger-Lise Lien	1982	1993	w	Norwegian social anthropologist	
1954	David Worrall	1983	2009		Australian composer and sound artist	
1954	Zoe Sofoulis	1983	1988		Australian director of the Institute of Cultural Histories and Futures	
1954	Ronnie Cann	1983	1984	2019	British Professor Emeritus Linguistics and English Language	
1954	David Clarke	1983	1983	2017	British professor of modern and contemporary art	
1954	Mark Turner	1983	1983		American cognitive scientist, linguist, and author (
1954	Mare Koiva	1983	1990	w	Estonian leading researcher, Estonian Literary Museum (folkloristics, charms, religious studies, net lore, digital humanities)	
1954	Donald Ringe	1983	1984		American linguist and Indo-Europeanist	
1954	Zipora Cochavi-Rainey	1983	1989	w	Israeli linguist	
1954	Zahra Kamalkhani	1983	1996	w	Iranian anthropologist	
1954	Daniel Miller	1983	1983		British anthropologist who is closely associated with studies of human relationships to things and the consequences of consumption	
1954	James Petersen	1983	1983	2005	American anthropologist and archaeologist working in the Brazilian Amazon	1954-2005
1954	Giulia Sissa	1983	1983	w	Italian classical scholar and historian of philosophy	
1954	Maud Lavin	1984	1989	w	American nonfiction writer and cultural historian	

1954	Anthonia Kalu	1984	1984	w	American professor in the Department of Comparative Literature and Foreign Languages and Department of Gender and Sexuality Studies	
1954	Gülzura Cumakunova	1984	1984	w	Kyrgyz linguist	
1954	Roland Viau	1984	1991	2015	Canadian academic and writer	
1954	William Balée	1984	1984		American professor of anthropology (historical ecology and ethnobotany)	
1954	Ruxandra Demetrescu	1985	1999	w	Romanian Professor of Art History	
1954	Rajend Mesthrie	1985	1985		South African linguist	
1954	Kevin J. Hannan	1985			American ethnolinguist and slavist	1954-2008
1954	Wolfgang Schweickard	1985	1985		German Romance studies scholar and lexicographer	
1954	Theodore Louis Trost	1985	1998		American Professor in Religious Studies	
1954	David Fishelov	1986	1986		Israeli professor of comparative literature	
1954	Motti Regev	1986	1990		Israeli sociologist (Professor of Sociology and Cultural Studies)	
1954	Paul Bube	1986	1986		American the W. Lewis McColgan Professor of Religion	
1954	William Romanowski	1987	1990		American Professor of Communication Arts and Sciences	
1954	Alison Milbank	1987	1988	w	British the Anglican priest and British literary scholar (religion and culture)	
1954	Gary Edward McPherson	1987	1993		Australian music educator, academic and musician (musical development, music performance science and music psychology)	
1954	Eli Bentor	1987	1994		Israeli art historian (African art and performance)	
1954	Donald C. Jackman	1987	1987		American medievalist and linguist	
1954	Karl Baier	1987	1987		German Professor for Religious Studies	
1954	Michel Sirvent	1988	1988		French literary critic	
1954	Fitriaty Harahap	1988	No	2012 w	Indonesian Lecturer of History Literature	
1954	Bente Kiilerich	1988		w	Norwegian art historian	
1954	Helena Wulff	1988	1988	w	Swedish Professor of Social Anthropology	
1954	Nkiru Nzegwu	1988	1989	2019 w	Nigerian philosopher, painter, author, curator and art historian	
1954	Pim Valkenberg	1988	1990		Dutch the Ordinary Professor of Religion and Culture	
1954	Karl Olav Sandnes	1988	1988		Norwegian theologian	

1954	Yehoyada Amir	1988	1993		Israeli Professor of Jewish Thought, Hebrew Union College
1954	Irit Ziffer	1989		w	Israeli archaeologist and art historian
1954	Stephen Bury	1990	1990		British art historian and the Andrew W. Mellon Chief Librarian of the Frick Art Reference Library in New York City
1954	Jill Green	1991	1993	w	American dance educator and scholar (originated the Social Somatic Theory)
1954	Mohammad A. Quayum	1991	1991	2012 w	Bangladeshi academic, writer, editor, critic and translator
1954	Judit Gera	1991	1991	w	Hungarian Professor for Modern Dutch Literature
1954	Joyce Imali Wangia	1991	2003	w	Kenyan Senior lecturer of Department of English and Linguistics
1954	Janet Monge	1991	1991	w	American the keeper and curator of the physical anthropology section at the Penn Museum, the Associate Director and Manager of the Penn Museum Casting Program, Adjunct Associate Professor at the University of Pennsylvania, and Visiting Professor at Princeton University
1954	Alina Payne	1992	1998	w	Romanian-American the Alexander P. Misheff Professor of History of Art and Architecture at Harvard University
1954	John J. Coughlin	1992			American Global Distinguished Professor of Religious Studies and Law
1954	Frank Ugiomoh	1993	2003		Nigerian sculptor, printmaker and art historian is a professor of art history and theory in the Department of Fine Art and Design
1954	Ole Karlsen	1993			Norwegian professor of Nordic literature
1954	Tengku Silvana Sinar	1994	1996	2012 w	Indonesian Linguistics Professor at the Faculty of Cultural Sciences
1954	Linda Dryden	1995	1996	w	British Professor of English Literature
1954	James Hanges	1995	1999		American Professor Comparative Religion
1954	Hendrik Borgdorff	1998	2012		Dutch Professor of Research in the Arts
1954	Sonia Álvarez Leguizamón	2000	2003	w	Argentinean sociologist and anthropologist

1954	Manthos Santorineos	2003	2006		Greek new-media artist, researcher, and Associate Professor in Athens School of Fine Arts
1954	suhaini saleh	2005	No		Indonesian lecturer in English Department, Faculty of Languages and Arts
1954	Andi Qashas Rahman	2006	2006	w	Indonesian professor in Applied Linguistics